

**By The Numbers: What Determines Professional Soccer
Contracts At the Highest Level**

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Abstract

This research examines the relationship between player value and salary at the highest level of professional soccer, both within and across Europe's top leagues. This study examines cross-league valuation of players within the same position by analyzing performance and contract data from the last full season (2023-2024) across the top 5 professional European men's soccer leagues. Furthermore, It also tests for cross-league differences in player salaries and compares each position's share of total payroll. The methodology entails building detailed datasets—compiled of player attributes, performance data, and salary information—and applying correlation analysis, significance testing, and payroll allocation in order to uncover each league's demands and preferences for talent at each position, as well as what truly determines a player's salary.

Results show that, across the Big Five, distinct position-specific attributes are associated with higher salaries. Moreover, each league in the top 5 European leagues has their own preferences at each position largely due to their distinct playstyle; players with the qualities that a league prefers will also earn larger salaries.

Introduction

Soccer— primarily known as football — is a global phenomenon that is unique because nearly every nation indulges in the sport. While some countries invest in the sport more than others, the same 5 nations have been at the forefront since the beginning of the sport: France, England, Italy, Germany, and Spain. These five countries are home to the biggest, most competitive soccer leagues in the world, known as the European “Big Five”— Ligue 1, Serie A, Premier League, Bundesliga, and La Liga (Raj, 2024). Furthermore, these five leagues cumulatively obtain the greatest circulation of money and wealth, which funds player contracts for all the best players in the world.

Professional soccer contracts extend far beyond base salaries, incorporating signing and performance bonuses, release clauses, and transfer fees. Moreover, the emergence and influx of different revenue streams for clubs—endorsements, broadcasting deals, ticket sales, merchandise, club investment—has in turn created a spike in player contracts over time, especially in recent years: over the last 20 years, player contracts in the Big Five have increased by roughly 167%, with some leagues, specifically Serie A, climbing as high as 400%. Nevertheless, the circulation of money in the Big Five isn’t equally dispersed across all players, positions, clubs, or leagues. For instance, a generational player like Lionel Messi or Cristiano Ronaldo won’t be paid the same as the average player.

The objective of this research is to analyze the correlation between player performance and salary across the Big Five, a primarily unexplored area in professional soccer that doesn’t go deeper than the superficial idea that the better a player is, the higher their salary is expected to be. Specifically, this research aims to uncover how players of the same position are viewed differently between leagues, as well as which players are over- vs. under-valued. Ultimately, this

research will uncover the demands and preferences of each league for talent at each position, as well as what truly determines a player's salary.

Literature Review

To investigate the relationship between player performance and salary in Europe's Big 5, I surveyed the literature on player contract overview, the relationship between player salary disparity and team performance, the differences between each league in the Big 5, and the concept of a player's potential. Consequently, these pieces of literature helped develop my understanding of the construction of a player's contract and the justification for the allocation of greater salaries to more valuable players. Furthermore, I understood the main distinctions in playstyle between each league in the Big 5; moreover, I learned about the importance of potential on a player's overall value.

Professional Soccer Contract Overview

Before diving into what drives professional soccer contract value, it is important to understand the structure of the contracts themselves. Every professional soccer contract starts off with a base salary that tends to stay consistent unless players exceed expectations. In that case, players often receive bonuses, which can be in many different forms: minute-based bonuses, where players get paid extra if they play matches; personal bonuses, where players get paid extra if they meet certain statistical standards; achievement bonuses, where players get paid extra if the team reaches pre-agreed targets (winning trophies, surviving relegation, earning promotion etc); and loyalty bonuses, which are typically paid after a set number of completed contractual years as an incentive for the player not to seek a move elsewhere (Karlsen, 2025). Besides bonuses, players may also receive other add-ons such as signing-on fees or other minor perks. Moreover,

all the effort that goes into negotiating and finalizing a player's contract is done by their agent, who typically earns anywhere between 5-10% of the player's salary (Karlsen, 2025).

Justification for Salary Disparity Between Players

A study analyzed the relationship between salary disparity and team performance in the Premier League. This study quantified team performance with how many points each Premier League team had from 2013/14 to 2022/23; moreover, salary disparity was quantified with the Gini Coefficient, a statistical measure ranging from 0 to 1 used to measure inequality (0 represents perfect equality and 1 represents perfect inequality). The study's results displayed a weak correlation between the Gini Coefficient and points, resulting in the conclusion that there is no correlation between the equality of salary dispersion within a team and that team's on-pitch success (Morton & Traugatt, 2024). However, a positive factor with a direct relationship with points was the number of impact players—the top 20% of players with goal contributions—on a team; another one is FIFA rating (measurement of talent available to a team), which is reliable because they are based on performance metrics derived from real-world matches (goals, assists, tackles etc). Ultimately, the combination of a weak correlation between points and the salary Gini Coefficient, along with a strong correlation between points and the number of impact players on a team, justifies impact players receiving greater salaries, and vice versa.

Key Differences Between Each League in the Big Five

There are key differences in player value, respectively, to each league in the Big Five, as a result of the key differences in each league's playstyle. For instance, the Bundesliga is “fast and direct”, while also being known for gegenpressing – instantly putting pressure on the opposition

once the ball is lost. La Liga emphasizes a ‘fast and direct’ style but consistently ranks lower in goals and expected goals (Benson, 2024). Serie A is known for having a defensive playstyle: their possession play is “slow and intricate”, and they also rank near the bottom in regards to goals and expected goals (Benson, 2024). Ligue 1 tends to have a more varied style, with some teams favoring a “fast and direct” approach while others play more “slow and intricate”; this is supported by the fact that Ligue 1 was often the midpoint for metrics conveying attacking output and possession style – goals, expected goals, passes per sequence, direct speed upfield (Benson, 2024). Finally, the Premier League is known for playing “slow and intricate”; however, it is still at the top in terms of attacking output and counter-pressing–English for gegenpressing (Benson, 2024). Furthermore, the varied playstyles of each league in the Big Five subsequently affect the types of players prioritized by each league; in other words, one league might value a player substantially more than another because of their distinct qualities that fit that league’s playstyle. For example, a player who has strong athleticism but isn’t as technically sound may be more valuable in the Premier League or Bundesliga than in La Liga.

A separate study analyzing the relationship between salary and a player’s on-pitch performance found that the determination of salary for midfielders is based on what each league values: while the Premier League and Serie A value midfielders who score goals, create chances, and play forward passes, La Liga values midfielders who are defensive, deep-lying playmakers (Benson, 2024). This demonstrates the differences in what each league values in a player at each respective position.

Value Derived From Potential

In addition to the playstyle of the league in which a player is signed, future potential is also a key factor in determining player salary. One current example of the importance of potential on salary is Spanish center back Dean Hujisen. Among his other exceptional qualities (versatility, height, soccer IQ, ability to use both feet), Hujisen's value primarily comes from the fact that he has been standing out as a center back in the Premier League at the very young age of 19 (Akinwolere et al., 2025). Furthermore, Hujisen's exceptional on-field performance on the biggest stage at such a young age displays potential for him to develop into one of the best center-backs in the world when he enters his prime between the ages of 25 and 28. In other words, if a player at 27 years old was having the same season as Hujisen, they wouldn't have that same resale value that he currently has.

Materials and Methods

Data

Data collection consisted of player and performance data specific to the Big Five from the 2023-2024 season: the last full season. While it would be ideal to collect multiple seasons' worth of data to analyze, the scale of this research was limited due to time; therefore, I opted to focus on the most recent data available. The data is sourced from Football Reference, a comprehensive website dedicated to providing global football/soccer statistics (2023-2024 Big 5 European Leagues Stats | FBref.com, n.d.). Their data coverage is executed by Opta—a leader in football data analytics—who provide a combination of core event data (passes, shots, tackles) and advanced metrics (expected goals, expected assists, shot-creating actions, goal-creating actions).

The variables used from Football Reference are a combination of both foundational and advanced metrics relative to each position on the field. Evidently, goals and assists are key

variables that determine an attacking player's value; impact players – players who are at the top of G+A charts – are more valuable and obtain higher salaries than the average player. However, I also chose to include other key variables that apply to defending players: height, tackles, and clearances for centerbacks, along with saves and save percentage for goalkeepers. Furthermore, I also used advanced metrics such as chances created (shot-creating actions + goal-creating actions) for outfield players and expected vs. actual goals for goalkeepers. Lastly, in order to incorporate a player's potential, I added each player's age and their number of professional seasons played. The goalkeeper analysis will use 3 variables from Football Reference, and the outfield player analysis will use 9.

Moreover, data collection included player ratings from what is now called EA Sports FC, a video game franchise published and developed by EA Sports (Bauer, 2024). To break it down, these player ratings are determined by both qualitative and quantitative metrics. To elaborate, EA Sports is partnered with the FIFA Data Collection Network, a global network comprised of thousands of real-life football scouts, coaches and analysts; these contributors are tasked with collecting qualitative, subjective performance data of players from all around the world for further analysis, tracking attributes like speed, passing, shooting, dribbling, strength, etc. across club matches, international competitions and even training performances (Bauer, 2024).

Likewise, EA Sports has also partnered with Opta, who provide detailed datasets of player performance that obtain advanced statistics other than goals and assists; visualization tools like heat maps, radar charts, and action zones are used for positioning, play style (strengths and weaknesses), and spatial behavior, among other statistical measures (Bauer, 2024).

FIFA provides 5 key metrics for goalkeepers and 6 for outfield players. For goalkeepers, their overall value can be summed up by diving, handling, kicking, positioning, and reflexes.

Similarly, for outfield players, their overall value can be summed up by pace, shooting, dribbling, passing, defending, and physical. Each of these key metrics is composed of smaller statistical measures that collectively determine its quantitative value.

Utilizing the data specific to the Big Five from the 2023-2024 season, I compiled distinct datasets relative to player position and league (see Tables 1 and 2 in the results for detailed summaries of the datasets). To elaborate, stemming from the original dataset consisting of all the players, I created smaller datasets separated by player position. Subsequently, I took these smaller datasets and created even smaller datasets separated by league. In total, 24 datasets were created from the original dataset: 4 different positions and 6 different league requirements per position (one dataset for each league in the Big 5 + one dataset covering the Big 5 as a whole).

Correlation Analysis

For each of the 24 datasets, I ran correlation analysis for each of the several important performance metrics and FIFA ratings relative to each position, with the dependent variable consistently being player salary. Correlation analysis provides a simple way of understanding the relationship between an independent variable and a dependent variable, but it does not account for the impact of other variables. The correlation analysis conducted between player salary and any other variable will compute a numeric value between -1 and 1, which determines the strength of correlation: 1 is a perfect positive correlation, -1 is a perfect negative correlation, and 0 is no correlation.

Significance Testing

In order to test for significance in player salaries between any two leagues in the Big Five, I separated player salaries by position and league to create a total of 20 distinct datasets (4 positions across 5 different leagues). I conducted unpaired t-tests to determine the differences between player salaries at each position of any two leagues.

Results

Basic summary statistics

Table 1: Summary of Dataset Size

	Goalkeepers	Defenders	Midfielders	Forwards	Teams
EPL	40	224	260	216	20
La Liga	46	231	287	214	20
Ligue 1	33	203	260	212	18
Bundesliga	33	208	257	196	18
Serie A	51	246	258	204	20
Total	203	1112	1322	1042	96

Table 2: Average Salary (USD) by Position and League

	Goalkeepers	Defenders	Midfielders	Forwards
EPL	\$ 3,580,822	\$ 4,103,504	\$ 4,174,346	\$ 4,367,875
La Liga	\$ 2,411,188	\$ 2,330,355	\$ 2,694,021	\$ 2,689,374
Ligue 1	\$ 1,825,593	\$ 1,543,245	\$ 1,363,061	\$ 2,357,014
Bundesliga	\$ 2,530,284	\$ 2,213,694	\$ 2,032,137	\$ 3,329,280
Serie A	\$ 1,401,252	\$ 1,884,716	\$ 1,948,770	\$ 2,619,639

Payroll Allocation, Significance Testing, and Correlation Analysis

Goalkeepers

Table 3: Percentage of Total Payroll Allocated to Goalkeepers Across the Big Five

	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A
% of Payroll	8.29%	9.60%	10.02%	10.92%	7.60%

Table 4: Comparison of Goalkeeper Salaries Across the Big Five

	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A
EPL					
Ligue 1	.9699				
La Liga	.6601	.7068			
Bundesliga	.5355	.5787	.8186		
Serie A	.6511	.6428	.3545	.2842	

**Denotes statistical significance at the 95% confidence level*

Table 5: Correlation Analysis between Salary and Goalkeeper Performance Metrics

Goalkeepers	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A	All Leagues
Age	0.073	0.127	0.101	0.279	0.315	0.171
Appearances	0.514	0.089	0.128	0.153	0.384	0.232
Saves	0.275	0.101	0.112	0.079	-0.010	0.078

Save						
Percentage	0.405	0.091	0.071	0.071	0.287	0.181
Expected vs.						
Actual Goals						
Against	0.364	0.238	-0.012	0.029	0.049	0.100
Clearances	0.299	-0.001	-0.076	0.239	0.160	0.113
Height	0.002	0.005	0.139	0.171	0.054	0.101
Seasons played	0.167	0.251	0.284	0.429	0.416	0.309
Diving Rating	0.802	0.690	0.507	0.617	0.545	0.581
Hands Rating	0.736	0.611	0.662	0.556	0.575	0.601
Kicking Rating	0.641	0.272	0.378	0.520	0.417	0.462
Reflex Rating	0.770	0.655	0.578	0.507	0.501	0.566
Positioning						
Rating	0.771	0.648	0.536	0.681	0.567	0.593

The salary distribution results in Table 3 show how the largest allocation of money to goalkeepers as a fraction of a league's entire payroll is in La Liga (10.02%), whilst the smallest is in Serie A (7.60%). However, the t-test results in Table 4 support the conclusion that there is no statistically significant difference in a goalkeeper's average salary across Europe's Big Five. Despite the equality in average goalkeeper salary across leagues, the correlation analysis results in Table 5 establish that what determines goalkeeper salary varies by league. For example, the EPL places a greater importance on in-game goalkeeper performance metrics compared to the

rest of the Big 5. Conversely, La Liga places little to no importance on the same in-game metrics. The EPL and Serie A place greater weight on availability, proxied by appearances. Regarding experience (age, seasons played), both the Serie A and Bundesliga value it more. In Ligue 1, foot-skills metrics (e.g., kicking ratings, clearances) correlate less with goalkeeper pay than hand-skills metrics.

Although goalkeepers earn the least among all positions, their salaries across the Big Five show the strongest positive correlation with FIFA ratings; these FIFA ratings have a significantly stronger correlation with player salary than the in-game performance metrics— saves, save percentage, expected vs. actual goals against and clearances—which have little to no positive correlation with player salary. Apart from in-game goalkeeper performance metrics, the other variables with a weak positive correlation are age and height (although height may not be a factor because goalkeepers in the Big Five are already tall; therefore, there isn't a ton of differentiation in height compared to the differentiation in salary). Following FIFA ratings, the variables with the strongest positive correlation with player salary are seasons played and appearances. This demonstrates the importance of goalkeepers in the Big Five to have experience in playing professional soccer and the ability to stay healthy throughout the season to receive higher salaries.

Defenders

Table 6: Percentage of Total Payroll Allocated to Defenders Across the Big Five

	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A
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% of Payroll	40.38%	37.63%	37.91%	40.80%	40.91%
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Table 7: Comparison of Defender Salaries Across the Big Five

	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A
EPL					
Ligue 1	.0020				
La Liga	.8354	.0035			
Bundesliga	.3590	.0345	.4714		
Serie A	.2701	.0443	.3701	.8800	

*Denotes statistical significance at the 95% confidence level

Table 8: Correlation Analysis between Salary and Defender Performance Metrics

D - By League	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A	All Leagues
Age	0.321	0.247	0.252	0.148	0.418	0.276
Appearances	0.223	0.112	0.162	0.212	0.257	0.188
Goals	0.189	0.139	0.184	0.145	0.337	0.180
Assists	0.119	0.135	0.141	0.279	0.232	0.177
Tackles	0.176	0.048	0.088	0.150	0.213	0.143
Clearances	0.160	0.020	0.041	0.098	0.134	0.110
Chances Created	0.266	0.128	0.196	0.351	0.310	0.249

Height	0.132	0.043	-0.031	0.033	0.011	0.038
Seasons played	0.313	0.312	0.365	0.295	0.452	0.357
Pace Rating	-0.421	0.184	0.209	0.361	0.065	-0.012
Shooting Rating	-0.194	0.524	0.473	0.608	0.278	0.295
Passing Rating	0.653	0.472	0.530	0.740	0.581	0.511
Dribbling Rating	0.277	0.463	0.596	0.761	0.503	0.463
Defense Rating	0.945	0.248	0.075	0.511	0.354	0.349
Physicality Rating	0.888	0.253	0.314	0.440	0.367	0.290

The salary distribution results in Table 6 show that the largest allocation of money to defenders as a fraction of a league’s entire payroll is in Serie A (40.91%), whilst the smallest is in Ligue 1 (37.63%). The t-test results displayed in Table 7 indicate that average defender salaries in Ligue 1 exceed those in the EPL, La Liga, Bundesliga, and Serie A ($p = 0.002, 0.0035, 0.0345, 0.0443$). Moreover, the correlation analysis results in Table 8 corroborate that player salaries for defenders are driven by different combinations of variables relative to each league. In the EPL, clubs don’t want dynamic defenders who can attack with pace and shooting; instead, physicality and defending ability are the two variables that dictate player salary substantially more in the EPL than the rest of the Big Five. That being said, immensely more than the EPL, the Bundesliga values defenders that possess more attacking qualities, such as

pace, shooting, dribbling, and even passing. However, when it comes to defending ability, the league obtaining the lowest correlation with player salary is La Liga (in fact, the correlation value is extremely close to zero); rather, similar to the Bundesliga, La Liga values defenders who obtain on-ball ability—shooting, passing, dribbling—which makes sense given the league’s technical, possessive playstyle. In continuity with goalkeepers, Serie A defenders who are more experienced (age, seasons played) tend to receive higher salaries. Moreover, the Serie A values defenders who score goals and provide assists, which shows they look for complete defenders.

Looking at the Big 5 in its entirety, height and pace aren’t important factors when determining player salary for defenders. Instead, the Big Five cares more about technical ability (passing and dribbling rating) and experience (seasons played), apart from the evident defensive qualities a defender must already possess.

Midfielders

Table 9: Percentage of Total Payroll Allocated to Midfielders Across the Big Five

	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A
% of Payroll	27.31%	23.46%	31.16%	23.91%	26.96%

Table 10: Comparison of Midfielder Salaries Across the Big Five

	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A
EPL					
Ligue 1	.1050				
La Liga	.3021	.0064			
Bundesliga	.1462	.8536	.0105		

Serie A	.3636	.4784	.0486	.5950	
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**Denotes statistical significance at the 95% confidence level*

Table 11: Correlation Analysis between Salary and Midfielder Performance Metrics

MF - By League	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A	All Leagues
Age	0.302	0.270	0.193	0.272	0.407	0.253
Appearances	0.258	0.212	0.213	0.185	0.363	0.231
Goals	0.369	0.244	0.297	0.182	0.416	0.299
Assists	0.396	0.442	0.387	0.306	0.456	0.381
Tackles	0.209	0.134	0.214	0.159	0.313	0.214
Clearances	0.105	0.051	0.145	0.062	0.214	0.126
Chances Created	0.438	0.355	0.381	0.292	0.436	0.376
Height	0.014	0.095	0.003	-0.061	-0.129	-0.019
Seasons played	0.323	0.434	0.324	0.425	0.467	0.369
Pace Rating	-0.384	-0.660	-0.331	-0.032	0.027	-0.145
Shooting Rating	0.457	0.249	0.315	0.545	0.374	0.333
Passing Rating	0.607	0.339	0.489	0.615	0.545	0.449
Dribbling	0.503	0.474	0.375	0.661	0.546	0.388

Rating						
Defense Rating	0.536	0.097	0.267	-0.017	0.453	0.217
Physicality Rating	0.100	0.209	0.097	0.124	0.260	0.126

The salary distribution results in Table 9 convey that the largest allocation of money to midfielders as a fraction of a league’s entire payroll is in La Liga (31.16%), whilst the smallest is in Ligue 1 (23.46%). The t-test results in Table 10 conclude that the average midfielder salary in La Liga is statistically lower than that of Ligue 1, Bundesliga, and Serie A (the p-values are respectively .0064, .0105, .0486). Furthermore, the correlation analysis results displayed Table 10 confirm that each league in the Big Five looks for different qualities instilled in their midfielders. Regarding defensive-minded midfielders (good defense and physicality rating, great number of tackles and clearances throughout the season), Serie A values these types of midfielders the most, with the EPL and La Liga following close behind; additionally, both the Serie A and EPL also value midfielders who can create chances, score goals, and provide assists. Ultimately, both leagues value all-around midfielders who can succeed on both the offensive and defensive ends. Furthermore, Serie A has the highest correlation with age and seasons played, once again emphasizing the league-wide value on experience. Player salaries for midfielders in the Bundesliga, similar to its defenders, have the greatest correlation with passing, shooting, and dribbling, displaying the league’s value for all-around technical skills. Although Ligue 1, for its midfielders, values professional experience (seasons played) and the ability to provide assists and create chances, the league values pace and defensive qualities (clearances, tackles) the least compared to the rest of the Big Five.

Overall, player salary for midfielders isn't determined by athleticism—height, pace, physicality. Instead, leagues across the Big 5 grant higher salaries to midfielders who have expertise in passing, as well as the ability to create chances and provide assists at the highest level.

Forwards

Table 12: Percentage of Total Payroll Allocated to Forwards Across the Big Five

	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A
% of Payroll	24.02%	29.30%	20.90%	24.47%	24.53%

Table 13: Comparison of Forward Salaries Across the Big Five

	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A
EPL					
Ligue 1	.0102				
La Liga	.1137	.2975			
Bundesliga	.2595	.1652	.6913		
Serie A	.1450	.2851	.9445	.7529	

**Denotes statistical significance at the 95% confidence level*

Table 14: Correlation Analysis between Salary and Forward Performance Metrics

FW - By						All
League	EPL	Ligue 1	La Liga	Bundesliga	Serie A	Leagues

Age	0.379	0.147	0.161	0.294	0.317	0.220
Appearances	0.396	0.185	0.254	0.139	0.427	0.262
Goals	0.467	0.516	0.491	0.364	0.686	0.471
Assists	0.411	0.391	0.406	0.349	0.455	0.390
Tackles	0.311	0.029	0.077	0.029	0.183	0.148
Clearances	0.161	-0.014	0.119	-0.037	0.266	0.086
Chances						
Created	0.486	0.322	0.363	0.281	0.435	0.375
Height	-0.046	-0.010	-0.028	-0.003	0.009	-0.031
Seasons played	0.419	0.256	0.299	0.445	0.419	0.339
Pace Rating	0.207	-0.277	0.333	-0.156	0.155	0.100
Shooting Rating	0.752	0.268	0.489	0.521	0.440	0.437
Passing Rating	0.570	0.324	0.433	0.770	0.745	0.478
Dribbling						
Rating	0.714	0.366	0.202	0.739	0.774	0.429
Defense Rating	0.181	0.179	0.000	0.128	-0.118	0.182
Physicality						
Rating	0.462	0.123	0.396	0.098	-0.095	0.227

The salary distribution results in Table 12 convey that the largest allocation of money to forwards as a fraction of a league's entire payroll is in Ligue 1 (29.30%), whilst the smallest is in La Liga (20.90%). The t-test results displayed in Table 13 only conclude that the average forward salary in Ligue 1 is statistically greater than that of the EPL (p-value = .0102). That being said, the correlation analysis results in Table 14 verify that each league has different criteria for what they look for in their forwards. For instance, the Serie A wants forwards who can do it all offensively: they value all-around technical ability (shooting, passing, dribbling) and chance production, along with the ability to score goals and provide assists. The EPL is very similar, except the league also values defensive work and physicality more than the rest of the Big Five; this is understandable considering defensive tactical play in the EPL involves attackers tracking back and pressing the opposing team. Similarly, La Liga also values physicality, plus it values pace more than any other league in the Big Five. Conversely, Ligue 1 values pace the least compared to the rest of the Big Five; instead, they simply look for attackers who can score goals and provide assists. The Bundesliga, like the EPL and Serie A, looks for forwards with all-around technical ability; moreover, the league prioritizes professional experience (age, seasons played). Again, this is contrary to Ligue 1, which cares about experience the least when determining player salary for attackers.

Ultimately, forwards in the Big Five earn the most compared to other positions; to earn marginally higher salaries, they need to possess several specific traits. Most importantly, they have to score goals and provide assists. Moreover, they have to possess an all-around technical ability: shooting, passing, and dribbling. Certain traits are not prioritized in forwards;

specifically, defensive attributes have little influence on their salaries. Furthermore, concerning physical ability, qualities such as height, physicality, and surprisingly pace are all irrelevant.

Discussion

Future research could expand the dataset by incorporating additional seasons and a wider range of variables. Additional variables could include crosses stopped for goalkeepers, aerial duels won for defenders, pass completion percentage for midfielders, and 1v1 attacking success for forwards. Moreover, breaking down each position into more specialized roles would have enhanced the analysis by determining which distinct variables have the most effect on each subposition rather than the generalized position. Lastly, with more time and access to additional resources, statistical analysis could have gone a step further by creating an equation for each position with the ability to predict player salary based on a combination of player qualities and on-field performance.

The findings from this research are vital towards understanding what truly determines a player's salary at the highest level of professional soccer. Similar statistical analysis methods can be applied to other professional soccer leagues, but also to other major sports leagues: NBA, NFL, MLB, NHL, cricket, and other massive sports industries. Ultimately, with larger datasets, better statistical models, and more detailed positional roles, this method of analysis may aid players in understanding which league would give them the highest payout. Furthermore, professional soccer clubs would be able to comprehend which players are being undervalued or overvalued, allowing them to allocate proper salaries based solely on player value.

Conclusion

This research has provided valuable insight into the overarching correlation between a soccer player's value and their salary. Regarding the entire Big Five, each position has certain qualities that will make a player rise above and earn a higher salary. Furthermore, each league in the Big Five has its own preferences for each position largely due to its distinct playstyle; players with the distinct qualities that a league values will also be rewarded with greater pay.

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